

Teaching ethics as practice in clinical, counselling and educational psychology

In the education and training of postgraduate students in professional psychology, ethics and law are often encountered as dense regulatory material. Students are expected to master the guidelines, professional rules of conduct and legislation of the Health Professions Council of South Africa (HPCSA), frequently in preparation for their Professional Board Examinations.

Prof Jarred Martin, an Associate Professor in the Department of Psychology, explains that, while this knowledge is essential, ethics can be experienced as something to memorise rather than practise. "In professional life, however, ethical decision-making is rarely solitary, theoretical or straightforward. It is dialogical, contextual and frequently requires consultation across disciplinary areas of competence and expertise."

This is a challenge encountered by master's students in the two streams of Psychology presented in the Faculty of Humanities (clinical and counselling psychology), as well as in educational psychology, which is presented in the Faculty of Education. To shift this paradigm, lecturers in the three individual psychology disciplines at the University of Pretoria (UP) – Prof Jarred Martin (clinical psychology), Prof Tharina Guse (counselling psychology) and Prof Linda Theron (educational psychology) – designed and facilitated an interdisciplinary three-day workshop for postgraduate students, which provided an opportunity to rehearse collaborative and ethical decision-making.

FACULTY OF HUMANITIES

FACULTY OF EDUCATION

PROF JARRED MARTIN, PROF THARINA GUSE, PROF LINDA THERON

It modelled the interdisciplinary cooperation that students are encouraged to enact in their own ethical decision-making. “Rather than teaching ethics as policy,” says Prof Martin, “the workshop treated ethics as a simulation of professional practice.”

Although the workshop has been presented in the Department of Psychology since 2020, a change came about in 2025 when it was positioned within the Interdisciplinary School of Psychology (ISOP), a collaborative initiative that connects psychology-related departments in different faculties at UP to support shared teaching, research and practice. This enabled the presenters to break down disciplinary silos in professional psychology training through structured cross-programme case consultations. It also illustrated how interdisciplinary collaboration in teaching can mirror the collaborative realities of professional psychology. When ethics is taught as practice rather than policy, it becomes a powerful space to prepare future psychologists for the complexities of real-world professional life.

ETHICS AS A LIVE, SOCIAL PROCESS

Prof Martin explains that the students' preparation begins long before the workshop starts. In accordance with the practical, interactive nature of the workshop, students work together in programme-specific groups. “Instead of passively reading the HPCSA's guidelines and legislation, they co-create concise visual legislative summaries of allocated sections, transforming dense regulatory content into

a shared applied knowledge base.” These summaries become a collective knowledge base for the cohort. “Students move from being recipients of regulatory information to authors of learning resources for their peers.” The process requires them to interpret legislation, identify guiding principles and simplify complex legal language. “By the time the workshop begins, students have engaged deeply with the material as it applies to ethics and the law, and have contributed to a shared interdisciplinary repository that many later report using to prepare for their Professional Board Examinations.

The first day of the workshop introduces contemporary models of ethical decision-making. This is followed by a formative case scenario with multiple overlapping ethical dilemmas. “Students form interdisciplinary groups to analyse the scenario, drawing on the summaries they created with their peers. The opportunity to collectively apply ethical decision-making foregrounds ethical mindfulness that is sensitive to the complexity of practising psychology in the South African context.”

What follows over the next two days is not a series of lectures, but a rehearsal of professional ethical reasoning. Groups work through progressively complex case scenarios, which require the application of legislation, HPCSA rules of conduct and ethical principles, while negotiating differences in disciplinary competence between clinical, counselling and educational psychology. This process mirrors real professional consultation, where psychologists must ask: Whose expertise is most relevant? What does the law require? What would constitute an ethical

violation? What course of action is in the best interests of the patient or client? “Students begin to experience ethics not as a checklist, but as a nuanced process of reasoning that benefits from multiple perspectives.”

LEARNING FROM REAL COMPLAINTS

Prof Martin observes that the focus on real-world malpractice complaint cases has become increasingly prominent in recent years, and is a source of anxiety for many candidates. However, a session facilitated by Dr Hanlé Kirkcaldy, Head of the University's Student Counselling Unit, who has conducted extensive research on psychologists' experiences of malpractice complaints, grounds the workshop in professional reality. It provides students with insight into how ethical breaches are investigated, how complaints unfold at the Regulator, and the professional and personal impact these processes have on practitioners. “This perspective transforms ethics from an abstract requirement to a matter of professional responsibility, accountability and care, reducing ethics and law anxiety, while strengthening professional judgement.”

Prof Martin remarks that students frequently enter the workshop with apprehension about ethics and legislation. “Many report feeling overwhelmed by the volume of legal material, and express anxiety about becoming the subject of complaints or litigation once they are qualified and registered.” Ethics and law are often experienced as threatening domains that highlight professional risk rather than guidance.

“Paradoxically, engaging directly with these realities reduces this anxiety. As students work through case scenarios, consult across disciplinary expertise, and hear first-hand accounts of complaints processes, ethics and legislation shift from being abstract sources of fear to practical tools that support responsible decision-making.”

Ethical principles are reframed as aspirational guidelines to act in the client’s best interests. Students begin to see that ethical dilemmas are rarely resolved by individual certainty, but through careful reasoning, consultation and an understanding of professional scope. “What initially appears as intimidating legal complexity becomes a framework that can be navigated with confidence.”

PRACTISING PROFESSIONAL IDENTITY AND COLLABORATION

On the final day of the workshop, the focus shifts to professional identity, registration categories and disciplinary competence. Students reflect on how their areas of expertise shape ethical responsibility and how consultation with colleagues from other psychology disciplines strengthens ethical decision-making.

This co-facilitation across the three psychology disciplines models the collaborative practice expected of future registered psychologists. They therefore gain first-hand experience of the scope of the profession. They understand the limits of their own specialised competence and the value of peer input, rehearsing the interdisciplinary conversations psychologists regularly engage in when faced with complex dilemmas.

“**Working with students from other psychology disciplines really showed me how important collaboration is. It made ethics feel like something you can actually figure out together.**”

– **Clinical Psychology student**

“**Before the workshop, ethics and law felt really overwhelming because the ethical code is so long and there are so many different laws to keep track of. But working through real ethical and legal dilemmas and hearing how others think about them made it feel much more manageable and actually relevant to how I’ll work one day as a psychologist.**”

– **Counselling Psychology student**

Pedagogically, the workshop achieves several outcomes simultaneously. It transforms legislation into applied reasoning, positions students as collaborators in learning, fosters interdisciplinary consultation, and supports preparation for Board Examinations as a by-product rather than the primary goal.

Most importantly, it contributes to professional identity formation. “Students do not leave with only knowledge of the rules that govern psychology; they leave having practised being psychologists who can navigate those rules together.”

Informal feedback consistently highlights how different this experience feels from traditional ethics teaching.

Many students note that the workshop is the first time that ethics “makes sense” as something they will do rather than write about. Others report that creating summaries for peers deepened their understanding more than reading documents alone.

“**I thoroughly enjoyed the ethics workshop, particularly the structured, step-by-step guidance in engaging with ethical dilemmas. It transformed ethics from something theoretical into a practical process.**”

– **Educational Psychology student**

In professional life, ethical decision-making rarely happens in isolation. It is shaped by context, consultation, legislation and professional judgment. By simulating this reality in the classroom, the workshop bridges the gap between regulatory knowledge and professional practice. By the time students leave, they have moved from reading about ethics to rehearsing ethical practice. They begin to understand that ethical competence in psychology is not only about knowing the guidelines, but about knowing how to think, consult and act within them as part of a professional community. ■